

Factors Influencing the Intention to Become an Entrepreneur: The Study Based on Undergraduate Students in Srilanka

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Abstract

This study develops and tests a model that aims to explain undergraduate students' entrepreneurial intention by considering the close environmental factors of the respondents such as closer valuation of entrepreneurship and the closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and the mediating role of individual innovative cognitive style. In this study, the primary data were collected via questionnaire. Structured questionnaire was distributed to Faculty related to Commerce and Management final year undergraduate students from five selected state universities in Sri Lanka, the universities are Eastern University, Sri Lanka, University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka, University of Ruhuna Sri Lanka and University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka and obtained 380 responses from the respondents.

In this study Cronbach's alpha analysis, Univariate Analysis, Bivariate Analysis and Regression Analysis were used for analysis. As per the findings the entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure level is high among the faculty related to Commerce and Management final year undergraduate students from five state universities in Sri Lanka. Moreover, the results indicated that partially mediation influence of individual innovative cognitive style to the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure.

Key words: *Entrepreneurial Intention, Individual Innovative Cognitive Style, Closer valuation of Entrepreneurship, Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure*

Background of the Study

Entrepreneurship can be a procedure to generate new ventures and new organizations. (Tran & VonKorflesh,2016). Entrepreneurial activities generate job opportunities and various other economic benefits (Abdullah Azhar, Annum Javaid, Mohsin Rehman & Asma Hyder ,2010), so the entrepreneurship does not create employment for the particular entrepreneur it will create more employment opportunities for others and also it creates more economic benefits. The

entrepreneurship has a positive impact in decreasing poverty, encouraging innovation, developing the entrepreneurial economy, fostering economic growth, increasing employment, increasing the quality of employment, cultural exchange, taxation and self-efficacy (Wan Lingya ,2017).

Dugassa Tessema Gerba, (2012) state that entrepreneurial intention is the reflection of the state of the mind and directs people to carry out self-employment instead of being employed. The idea of becoming a self-employed person may be really attractive for the young graduates because it is often seen as a desirable form to participate in the economic activities without losing their personal independence (Nurye,2017). Mario Franco, Heiko Haase & Arndt Lautenschlager (2010) found that although many efforts to inform competent entrepreneurs and to support start – ups among graduate, it seems that in many developing countries the number of graduate’s entrepreneurs remain very small.

Various researchers have analyzed various factors which influence the entrepreneurship intention of the individuals, but this study focus on to investigate how the close environmental factors such as closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure influencing the entrepreneurship intention of the Faculty related to Commerce and Management final year undergraduate students and the mediating effect of individual innovative cognitive style. This is the very first study which applies the individual innovative cognitive style as a mediating variable in the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and entrepreneurial intention and it tries to understand how this mediating variable individual innovative cognitive style plays an important role in shaping these relations.

Problem Statement

The advancement of educated youth is a positive development in a country: however, the labor market in many countries in the world unable to accommodate the expanding pool of the talented young graduates (Nurye,2017). In Ethiopia there are many educated youth are complaining for high levels of unemployment and they are looking for a job for several years by being unemployed (Nurye, 2017), As well as Ethiopia, Sri Lanka also came for the state of fasters growing economy in Asia since 2014 (DailyNews,2014) and Sri Lanka also facing the same problem as Ethiopia, because there is a high rate of unemployment among the youth generation in Sri Lanka. (Damayanthi Edirisinghe & Nimeshi, 2016) and also Damayanti Edirisinghe & Nimeshi (2016) state that in 2015 the youth unemployment rate was 21.7% and at that time that was reported as the highest unemployment rate. This particular situation is continuing in Sri Lanka. At present the Quarterly report of the Sri Lanka Labor Force Survey 2020 reported that the youth unemployment rate has been increased to 25.7% at the fourth quarter of 2020 and also it reported this is a highest unemployment rate.

According to Damayanthi Edirisinghe & Nimeshi (2016) limited students have an intention to start a new venture. Because of this situation in Sri Lanka the percentage of employers has been decreased to 2.3% at the fourth quarter of 2020, compared to 2.6% in 2019. So, Sri Lankan youth has the need to come forward in entrepreneurship and also our country is a developing country, so the entrepreneurial involvement will help the country for its development and also that will help to reduce the increasing youth unemployment.

Research Questions

1. What are the levels of entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure in the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka?
2. What is the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure in the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka?
3. Does individual innovative cognitive style mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure of the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka?

Research Objectives

1. To assess the levels of entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure in the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka.
2. To explore the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure in the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka.
3. To explore the mediating effect of individual innovative cognitive style in the relationship between entrepreneurial intention, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure of the faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurship

Now a days entrepreneurship has become one of the most essential activity for the development of a country's economy, because the advancement of entrepreneurial activities will lead to generation of opportunities for the various sectors of the society (Azhar, Javaid & Rehman, 2010), but defining entrepreneurship and entrepreneur is a hard task (Wickramasinghe,

Dedunu & Weerasinghe, 2017). However, Miller (1983) defeated the challenge and defined entrepreneurship as an organizational phenomenon that focuses on innovation, risk taking and proactiveness and Longenecker, Moore & Petty (2005) defined entrepreneurship as “when a person finds needs which exist in a market and establish a new business in order to address said needs, then obtaining income, profits, and social recognition”. There are many definitions for entrepreneurship, some researchers are perceiving entrepreneurship as a process of successful organization and other scholars define entrepreneurship as developing mind set and skills (Diandra & Azmy, 2020). However, finally Hessels & Naude (2019) defined entrepreneurship as “which is generating job opportunities and lead to economic development” and also Hessels & Naude (2019) highlighted that, the entrepreneurial skill will bring innovation to the market through entrepreneurship process.

Several researchers classify entrepreneurship into different types. Barot (2015) state that there are two types of entrepreneurship, they are opportunity -based entrepreneurship and necessity-based entrepreneurship. According to He, Nazari, Zhang, and Cai (2020) the opportunity- based entrepreneurship is initiating venture activity because of new idea and personal amplifications and the necessity- based entrepreneurship means the new entrepreneur has no option to earn for his or her living, in this stage the entrepreneurship is not the choice but it is compulsion (Barot, 2015) and in this stage people do not value the entrepreneurship because the situation is exist when there is no other labor market option (Gries & Naude, 2011). Aulet & Murray (2013) divided entrepreneurship into two types, they are innovation- driven entrepreneurship and small business entrepreneurship or small medium enterprises. The innovation- driven entrepreneurship means which shares the idea of innovation in business with purpose to pursue the global opportunities and the small business entrepreneurship or small medium enterprises means which serve local markets with traditional way with low competitive advantage and has the limited approach to the international market (Aulet & Murray, 2013).

Chell, Haworth & Brearley (1991) pointed out that, the entrepreneurs are more innovative and they won't relax until they achieve their goals. Furthermore, they have high risk-taking propensity, they will cope with complexity and uncertainty and they have a high tolerance of ambiguity (Brockhaus, 1980: Busenitz & Lau, 1996).

Entrepreneurial Intention among undergraduate students

Carr & Sequeira (2007): Himieleski & Corbett (2008): Wilson, Kickul & Marlino (2007) state that individual entrepreneurial intention has proven to be an essential and continuing construct in entrepreneurship research. The entrepreneurial intention is the initial step in the long process of venture creation (Linan & Chen, 2009) and it is a driving force which people utilize to generate a new ground of business (Li, Wu & Wu, 2008). Ajzen (1991) defined the intention as “indication of how hard the people are willing to try, how much of effort they are planning to exert, to carry out

the behavior.” and also the entrepreneurial intention has the reflection towards the state of mind that initiate the individuals to become desirable in self-employment rather than selecting the traditional salary-based employment (Gerba,2012).

Within the entrepreneurial context, the theory of planned behavior which is postulated by Ajzen (1991) been the most adopted theory in the entrepreneurial intention research. According to Ajzen(1991), the intention can be significantly predicted by a specific set of beliefs. They are beliefs about the outcomes of being an entrepreneur, beliefs about the normative expectations and perceived pressures of others regarding the choice of being an entrepreneur and beliefs about the existence of factors that may enhance or hinder performance of the possible future entrepreneurial role (Ajzen,2002;Linan&Chen,2009).

Factors Influencing Entrepreneurial Intention of Undergraduate students.

Closer valuation of entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention

According to North (1990) the closer valuation of entrepreneurship is an informal factor which plays a role in the configuration of entrepreneurial intention. The individuals receive the influence from closer environment valuation and this contribute to the creation of new start-up (Cooper & Dunkelberg,1988). Santos,Roomi&Linan(2016) state that, the closer valuation of entrepreneurship contributes to the generation of a favorable or unfavorable perception in the development of a new business. According to Iakovleva, Kolvereid and Stephan (2011) the social environment pressures can become a trigger for the development of an entrepreneurial career. If a person’s closer environment is supportive of entrepreneurship, then the person will be very interested to become an entrepreneur (Katono, 2011).

There are multiple social supportive sources which helps the individuals while they are willing to start a new venture (Sahban & et al, 2016). Various scholars have identified a variety of sources such as family, neighbors, friends, colleagues, community organizations and etc. (Farooq, Salam, Ur Rehman, Fayolle, Jaafar & Ayupp, 2018). The family’s opinion, close friends opinion and opinion of colleagues plays an important role to influence the individuals decisions to become an entrepreneur (Aldrich & Cliff,2003: Ambad & Damit,2016: Nanda &Sorensen,2010). Linan et al, (2011b) state that, the closer valuation exerts a stronger influence over personal attitude toward the behavior, while Martins & Perez (2020) also found that there is a positive relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial intention.

Therefore, the following hypothesis is presented:

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention

Closer stigma of entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention

According to Mc Grath(1999) the failure is an important event in entrepreneurship. Whyley (1998) state that the failure is a painful experience for entrepreneurs, because if a failure occurs that will damage particular entrepreneur image and confidence in the particular business, so every individual has this fear of failure. According to Grichnik, Smeja and Welps (2010) the fear is an emotional element which can work against entrepreneurial tasks and entrepreneurial efforts and also the entrepreneurial intention is determined by several factors but the fear of failure is at top of the list (Wickramasinghe, Dedunu & Weerasinghe,2017). Now a days most of the researcher's interest increasing on the stigma of entrepreneurship failure (Singh, Corner & Pavlovich, 2015). The stigma is the denigration or stain the person experiences, which negatively affects his or her image and prestige (Goffman, 1968). Stigma is defined generally as a mark of shame or infamy, a stain on one's prestige (Singh & et al., 2015).

Wickramasinghe & et al. (2017) state that, the stigma is a significant barrier to the entrepreneurial activities. The stigma of business failure systematically influences the willingness of the entrepreneurs to start a new business or to participate in risky activities (Armour & Cumming, 2008) and also it influences the choice of projects and the decision to terminate a project (Landier,2005).Baumol,(1993) highlighted that the societal perception of business failure has more suggestions for the perceptions of risk and the level of entrepreneurial activity within that society so it can be conclude that greater the stigma brought up by the closer environment and it will negatively influence the young individuals desire to enter into a new venture (Martins & Perez, 2020).

Therefore, the following hypothesis is presented:

H2: There is a significant negative relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention.

Individual Innovative Cognitive Style and Entrepreneurial Intention

Research about individual cognition has been broadly present in organizational behavior literature and it has been seen as a possibly relevant field in explaining the entrepreneurial behavior by several researchers (Krueger.2007: Pihie, Bagheri&Sani,2013). According to Hunt, Krzystofiak, Meindle and Yousry (1989) the cognitive style means it is the way people process and organize information and come for a conclusion on the basis of their observations and also cognitive style was defined by Cools, Broeck & Bouckenoghe (2009) as "the way people perceive stimuli and how they use this information to guide their behavior". Barbosa, Gerhardt &Kickul (2007) state that an individual's cognitive style will influence individual's options for different types of knowledge gathering, learning, information processing and decision making, many of the critical behavior with which an entrepreneur is focused on a daily basis, and also the

cognition has the potential to make a remarkable contribution to the study of entrepreneurship (Allinson&Hayes,1996).

According to Cassidy (2004) various scholars have tried to create order in the cognitive style field by combining and categorizing different theories and many researchers have found various variety of cognitive style dimensions (Kozhevnikov, 2007) and the results of empirical research on the relationship between different cognitive style measures proposed that cognitive style is a complex variable with multiple dimensions (Beyler & Schmeck, 1992: Leonard,Scholl&Kowalski,1999). Rogers (1983) defines the innovativeness as” the extent to which individual or institutional adopter adopts new ideas relatively earlier than do other members of population or social system” and some other researchers define innovativeness as the result of innovative cognitive style (Kirton,1976).

Innovation is a characteristic of entrepreneurs as they have to see and grab the opportunities where other people do not find out them and provide creative and innovative solutions (Armstrong & Hird,2009). Innovative entrepreneurs have more desirable to challenge assumptions and also innovative entrepreneurs have creative intelligence, which allows discovery yet differs from other types of intelligence (Dyer,Gregersen, & Christensen, 2009). Many researchers such as Hurt,Joseph&cook(1977) and Kirton (1976) measures the innovative cognitive style by using several scales and most of the scholars investigated an impact of innovativeness on entrepreneurial intention by utilizing the Kirton scale(Pejic&et.al,2018), so after considering previous scholars dimensions of innovative cognitive style Goldsmith (1991) proposed four dimensions of innovativeness they are willing to try, Creative original, Opinion leader and Ambiguities problems. Meredith, Nelson & Neck (1982). state that successful entrepreneurs have high level of self -confidence and they are more willing to try something new that others viewed as a risk. Therefore, can be assume that when an individual willing to try ability increases that will lead them towards a successful entrepreneurship involvement. According to Fillis and Rentschler (2006) creativity is a innovative skill which being able to do inventive things and the things which are non- routine, while also building on tradition to reach profitable outcomes. Lee, Florida & Acs (2004) state that the entrepreneurial activity needs an environment where the creativity can flourish. Therefore, when the creativity increases the entrepreneurial activities also increase. According to Valente and Pumpuang (2007) the opinion leaders are the people who influence the opinions, attitudes, beliefs, motivations and behaviors of others. Opinion leadership most often attempts to explain how new ideas and practices spread within and between communities (Rogers, 2003).

Arend (2020) define ambiguity as follow “ambiguity means which exists when the set of future possible outcomes are known, as is the set of actions possible to take, as are the payoffs for each action in each outcome, but the perfect probabilities of those outcomes are all unknowable earlier to having to make the decision.” Entrepreneurs are frequently required to make decisions with

insufficient information, which creates ambiguity (Gurel, Altinay & Daniele, 2010) but they have the tendency to perceive ambiguous situations as desirable (Begley & Boyd, 1987). Therefore, entrepreneurs will have the capacity to tolerate the ambiguity (Schere,1982). Teoh & Foo (1997) state that many entrepreneurial decisions will involve with ambiguity in that the decisions result in actions that are innovative and original. Martins&Perez (2020) found that there is positive relationship between innovation and entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, it can be reliable that, the individual innovative cognitive style will positively influence the entrepreneurial intention.

Therefore, the following hypothesis presented:

H3: There is a significant positive relationship between Individual Innovative Cognitive Style and Entrepreneurial Intention.

The mediating role of individual innovative cognitive style

The close environment of the individual has a positive or negative thought about the entrepreneurship, therefore it is expected that, the individual's entrepreneurial intention will be influenced desirably or not desirably (Linan&et,al,2011:Santos,Roomi&Linan,2016). Because the family, friends and colleagues influence individual's behavior (Ajzen,1991), this influence through individual innovative cognitive style can be impact the individual to engage in the entrepreneurial activities. Martins & Perez (2020) state that the individuals who were having the ability to innovate will have quite more confident in achieving the success of their ideas. Furthermore, the people who have entrepreneurial skills are quite better able to adapt situations which are not so favorable and handle them easily (Kolvereid&Isaksen, 2006) and also the people who are more innovative will create new solutions for the problem, do things differently and approach the problems from different angles (Hurt, Joseph & cook ,1977;Kirton ,1976 & Marcati & et, al, 2008).So, can be expect that, there is mediation influence of individual innovative cognitive style in the relationship between close environment factors and entrepreneurial intention.

Martins & Perez (2020) found that individual innovativeness positively related with closer valuation of entrepreneurship and also found that individual innovativeness positively related with closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure. Therefore, to examine the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and individual innovative cognitive style, the H4a and H5a created. Meanwhile, to examine the mediation influence of individual innovative cognitive style in the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and entrepreneurial intention, the H4b and H5b created.

Therefore, the following hypothesis presented:

H4a: There is a significant positive relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style.

H4b: There is a mediation influence of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style to the relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention

H5a: There is a significant positive relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style.

H5b: There is a mediation influence of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style to the relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention

3.1 Theoretic Support for the Conceptual Model

Ajzen’s Theory of Planned Behavior explains that the contextual factors influence entrepreneurial intention, through attitude toward a specific behavior and Shapiros Entrepreneurial Event Theory considers firm creation as the result of the interaction among contextual factors, which would act through their influence on the individual perceptions. Most essentially, these two theories agree that the individual’s behaviors would be the result of environmental factors.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Modified version of Martins & Perez, 2020

Research Methodology

The research philosophy of this study is positivism because in this study the researcher has a role of collecting and interpret through objective approach and the research findings are observable and quantifiable. This study has used a survey strategy or survey design. Survey strategy is usually connected with the deductive approach. The research has been conducted by using primary data.. Cross sectional method was used in this study when collecting primary data because the primary data were gathered for one-time purpose. The target population of this study is faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in Sri Lanka. This study adopts the stratified sampling technique. The research study used well-structured questionnaire which consists 36 questions was used as research instrument for data collection. The data were decided to obtained from 350 samples but 380 response were obtained from faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students in five selected state universities in Sri Lanka (Eastern University, Sri Lanka, University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka, University of Ruhuna Sri Lanka and University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka).

In this study Cronbach's alpha analysis, Univariate Analysis, Bivariate Analysis and Regression Analysis were used for analysis. According to Cronbach's Alpha Analysis if the Cronbach's Alpha Value is 0.7 and above it is considered as accepted reliable instrument (George & Mallery,2003). Under univariate analysis, researcher analysis the degree of variables, dimensions and indicators by using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Bivariate correlation tests whether the relationship between two variables is linear (as one variable increases the other variable also increase or as one variable increases and other variable decreases) (Kumar, 2014). the researcher has used the multiple regression analysis to find out the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable, so as to examine the relative influence of independent variables with respect to individual innovative cognitive style and entrepreneurial intention, in order to figure out which are important determinants of entrepreneurial intention. And also, in this study, the researcher has applied the regression models to find out whether individual innovative cognitive style mediates the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and entrepreneurial intention.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Analysis of Reliability

In this study also, the Cronbach's Alpha value for overall variables are above 0.7. Therefore, it is indicated that all the items considered as reliable.

Univariate Analysis

According to this analysis the objective one was analyzed and the results was obtained as there is a high level of entrepreneurial intention, individual innovative cognitive style, closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure in the faculty related to commerce and management final year under graduate students in Sri Lanka.

Bivariate Analysis

The researcher used Bivariate correlation analysis to find out the results regarding objective two and Hypothesis 1, 2,3,4a and 5a. According to this analysis the objective two and Hypothesis 1, 2,3,4a and 5a were analyzed and the results were obtained as there is a strong positive relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention ($r=0.932$) and H1 was accepted. There is a weak negative relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention ($r=-0.186$) and H2 was accepted. There is a strong positive relationship between Individual Innovative Cognitive Style and Entrepreneurial Intention ($r=0.825$) and H3 was accepted. There is a strong positive relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style ($r=0.835$) and H4a was accepted. There is a weak positive relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style ($r=0.244$) and H5a was accepted.

Simple Regression Analysis

The mediating role of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style to the relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention.

The effect of Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship on Entrepreneurial Intention was R is 0.932, that indicates that there is a strong relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention. R Square is 0.869. Adjusted R Square is 0.869. Therefore, it can be concluded that 86.9% of variability in Entrepreneurial Intention was explained by Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship. As per ANOVA table result, p- value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship explains the variation of Entrepreneurial Intention. Coefficient result shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship, there is an increase of Entrepreneurial Intention in 2.121 units.

The effect of Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship on Individual Innovative Cognitive Style was R is 0.835, it indicates that there is a strong relationship between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style. R Square is 0.697. Adjusted R Square is 0.696. Therefore, it can be concluded that 69.7% of variability in Individual Innovative Cognitive Style was explained by Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship. As per ANOVA table result, p - value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship explains the variation of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style. Coefficient results shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship, there is an increase of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style in 4.577 units.

The effect of both Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style on Entrepreneurial Intention was R is 0.936, it indicates that there is a strong relationship between Entrepreneurial Intention, Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly. R Square is 0.877. Adjusted R Square is 0.876. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was 87.7% of variability in Entrepreneurial Intention was explained by its Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly. As per ANOVA table result, p - value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly explain the variation of Entrepreneurial Intention. Coefficient results shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship, there is an increase in Entrepreneurial Intention in 1.827 units jointly. At the same time, every unit of increasing in Individual Innovative Cognitive Style, there is an increase of Entrepreneurial Intention in 0.064 units jointly.

Therefore, according to the above derived results, it can be concluded that Individual Innovative Cognitive Style playing a partial mediating role in the connection in between Closer Valuation of Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Intention and the $H4b$ was accepted.

The mediating role of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style to the relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention.

The effect of Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure on Entrepreneurial Intention was R is 0.186, it indicates that there is a weak relationship between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention. R Square is 0.035. Adjusted R Square is 0.032. Therefore, it can be concluded that 3.5% of variability in Entrepreneurial Intention was explained by Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure. As per ANOVA table result, p - value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure explains the variation of Entrepreneurial Intention. Coefficient result shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure, there is a decrease of Entrepreneurial Intention in 0.745units.

The effect of Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure on Individual Innovative Cognitive Style was R is 0.244, it indicates that there is a weak relationship between Closer Stigma of

Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style. R Square is 0.060. Adjusted R Square is 0.057. Therefore, it can be concluded that 6% of variability in Individual Innovative Cognitive Style was explained by Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure. As per ANOVA table result, p- value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure explains the variation of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style. Coefficient results shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure, there is an increase of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style in 2.356 units.

The effect of Individual Innovative Cognitive Style on Entrepreneurial Intention was R is 0.825, it indicates that there is a strong relationship between Individual Innovative Cognitive Style and Entrepreneurial Intention. R Square is 0.681. Adjusted R Square is 0.680. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was a 68.1% of variability in Entrepreneurial Intention was explained by Individual Innovative Cognitive Style. As per ANOVA table result, p- value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Individual Innovative Cognitive Style explains the variation of Entrepreneurial Intention. Coefficient results shows that every unit of increasing Individual Innovative Cognitive Style, there is an increase of Entrepreneurial Intention in 0.342units.

The effect of both Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style on Entrepreneurial Intention. R is 0.917, it indicates that there is a strong relationship between Entrepreneurial Intention, Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly. R Square is 0.841. Adjusted R Square is 0.840. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was 84.1% of variability in Entrepreneurial Intention was explained by its Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly. As per ANOVA table result, p- value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Individual Innovative Cognitive Style jointly explain the variation of Entrepreneurial Intention. Coefficient results shows that every unit of increasing in Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure, there is a decrease in Entrepreneurial Intention in 1.650 units jointly. At the same time, every unit of increasing in Individual Innovative Cognitive Style, there is an increase of Entrepreneurial Intention in 0.384 units jointly.

Therefore, according to the above derived results, it can be concluded that Individual Innovative Cognitive Style playing a partial mediating role in the connection in between Closer Stigma of Entrepreneurship Failure and Entrepreneurial Intention and H5b was accepted.

RECOMMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The universities can organize and launch continuous entrepreneur training programs for the undergraduates during their academic period. And this program should provide some knowledge to the students regarding when they start a new business how they should deal with the customers, how effectively they should manage the human and financial resources and how they should step by step increase their business performance.
- The university should encourage the students to be an innovative person. To develop the innovativeness among the undergraduate students the university can provide them multiple tasks for which they should think critically and should provide the output in an innovative way.
- The undergraduate students can collaborate with some successful entrepreneurs because of this collaboration they will gain more knowledge about how to become a successful entrepreneur and how to survive in the market successfully.

LIMITATION OF THIS STUDY

This research only consider five state universities in Sri Lanka and the sample size is 380 but if the number of universities and number of samples increases the results might be different and this study only consider faculty related to commerce and management final year undergraduate students. Further, this study seeks only to understand the influence of closer valuation of entrepreneurship and closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure on the entrepreneurial intention, and the mediating role of individual innovative cognitive style in the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and entrepreneurial intention.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

- Increase the target number of state universities in Sri Lanka.
- Future researchers can increase the sample size to make the study more effective.
- Proceed the same research with reference to other faculty undergraduate students, rather than the faculty related to commerce and management undergraduate students and also consider graduate students who were pass out from the university.
- Focus on exploring the relationship between closer valuation of entrepreneurship, closer stigma of entrepreneurship failure and entrepreneurial intention with other related mediating variables, than the individual innovative cognitive style.
- Future researchers can consider more other factors rather than this research.

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